

Original Research

Interaction of Governance in the Influence of Ownership Structure on Tax Avoidance

Aldira Isma Agusti¹ , Lilik Handajani, I Nyoman Nugraha Ardana Putra
Faculty of Economics and Business, University of Mataram, Mataram, Indonesia

Received 6 January 2025 Revised 22 January 2025 Accepted 30 January 2025

Abstract

This study aims to analyze the interaction of corporate governance as a moderator of the relationship between family and foreign ownership structure and tax avoidance. Secondary data were taken from the annual reports of manufacturing companies from 2018 to 2022, with sample size of 260 (Companies, years). This study uses a fixed effect model to test the hypothesis. The research results show that family ownership does not have a significant effect on tax avoidance. Meanwhile, foreign ownership has a positive and significant effect on tax avoidance. Corporate governance cannot moderate the influence of family ownership and foreign ownership on tax avoidance. Corporate governance actually weakens the relationship between the company's ownership structure and tax avoidance. The study emphasizes the importance of corporations fulfilling their tax obligations for long-term viability and investment security. It also highlights the role of the board of commissioners in directing management and enforcing regulations. The research aims to provide government input on corporations and taxpayers, influencing state revenue. It also serves as a foundation for addressing tax avoidance regulations, such as the Harmonization of Tax Regulations.

Keywords: Family ownership, foreign ownership, governance, tax avoidance.

¹ Corresponding author's Email: diradiradir07@gmail.com

Introduction

Taxes are essential for a nation's fiscal autonomy, influencing the magnitude of its budget. Corporations, particularly major enterprises, seek to enhance the wealth of their owners through profit generation (Krisyadi & Anita, 2022). To attain substantial profits, firms frequently participate in tax evasion, which entails utilizing loopholes in current legislation. This approach adversely affects the state when corporations fail to fulfill their tax obligations. Company insiders perceive taxes as a liability, leading to diminished profitability. To optimize profits, corporations implement techniques to mitigate the tax liability (Marfiana & Andriyanto, 2021). Data from the Directorate General of Taxes indicates that tax revenue targets and actual collections in Indonesia from 2018 to 2022 amounted to billions.

Table 1. Tax Objectives and Achievement Metrics

Years	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Target	1.424,00	1.577,60	1.198,82	1.229,60	1.784,00
Realization	1.315,90	1.332,10	1.069,98	1.231,87	2.034,50
	92,40%	84,40%	89,25%	100,19%	114,00%

Source: Directorate General of Taxes 2018-2022

Table 1 illustrates the variability of tax revenue from 2018 to 2022. In 2022, tax collection surpassed the established objective, whereas in 2019, tax revenue reached its lowest point in the past five years. According to Kovermann & Wendt (2019), the engagement of corporations in tax avoidance is intricately linked to the management's position inside the organization. Various variables compel corporations to pursue tax avoidance, including profitability, debt, company size, capital intensity, sales growth, and ownership structure. The company's choice to pursue tax avoidance is somewhat shaped by its ownership structure. In firms with fragmented ownership, agency conflicts are more common between management and shareholders (Sastrodiharjo & Mukti, 2024). In firms with a centralized ownership structure, the distinction between control and ownership is minimal, as the owner or principal shareholders has significant authority to supervise the organization (Marfiana & Andriyanto, 2021). The majority shareholders possess considerable power to govern a corporation, such as the ability to appoint the Board of Directors or the CEO. The principal owners hold a superior role compared to management, which can be replaced at any time if it fails to achieve the expected outcomes. The company's ownership structure, whether dominated by family or foreign shareholders, affects its tax policy decisions. Family owners, who often exert greater control over the company, may be more inclined to exploit tax avoidance to preserve family wealth (Chalevas et al., 2024). Simultaneously, foreign ownership may prompt corporations to implement more aggressive tax strategies owing to the pressure to optimize short-term profitability (Hasan et al., 2022).

In family-owned enterprises, the ownership structure typically includes family members as board directors or commissioners, rendering the owners and controllers of the company inseparable. This enables the family, as proprietors and managers of the company, to derive personal advantages at the expense of other shareholders, including

the government, one method being tax avoidance (Kovermann & Wendt, 2019). For example, Samsung in South Korea faced a major tax evasion scandal related to its family ownership structure. In this case, the Lee family controls the company through a complex holding structure, allowing them to reduce tax liabilities despite the company generating large profits. Although the company has a global reputation, this tax avoidance has caused significant regulatory issues (Shin, 2020).

Conversely, it is posited that family enterprises are more inclined to preserve a long-term reputation than to prioritize short-term tax avoidance. Aggressive tax evasion can jeopardize shareholder relationships and compromise the company's future stability. Consequently, families sometimes opt to adopt more conservative tax strategies despite possessing enhanced influence over the enterprise. Walmart, although possessing significant family ownership characteristics, chooses for a conservative tax policy and refrains from employing aggressive tax avoidance tactics. This may come from the recognition that a company's reputation is vital for long-term sustainability, and tax avoidance may damage its image among the public and tax authorities (Chakroun, & Ben Amar, 2024).

The phenomenon occurring in developing countries, such as Indonesia, shows that tax avoidance by family-owned businesses is often influenced by weaknesses in regulations and government oversight. In countries with weaker legal systems and more lenient tax oversight, family-owned businesses tend to engage more frequently in aggressive tax avoidance. In this case, the incentive for tax evasion becomes stronger due to the opportunity to exploit legal loopholes (Ibrahim et al., 2021).

In Indonesia, the relationship between foreign ownership structures and tax avoidance is also a relevant topic, especially with the increasing involvement of multinational companies and foreign investors in the Indonesian market. Companies with foreign ownership are more likely to pursue tax avoidance, as foreign investors often prioritize profit maximization and global tax evasion. In Indonesia, multinational corporations frequently employ diverse tax avoidance strategies, including the utilization of overseas affiliate businesses and the manipulation of tax rate disparities between nations to diminish their tax liabilities in Indonesia (Koay, & Sapiei, 2024).

Google Indonesia exemplifies a case of tax avoidance using a foreign-owned entity. Google employs a worldwide corporate framework to channel the majority of its revenue to jurisdictions with little tax obligations, such as Singapore. Despite Google's operations in Indonesia, the Indonesian government has investigated the company for potential tax avoidance, asserting that Google does not remit taxes proportional to its earnings generated in the country (Nurdiansyah, 2023). While several foreign-owned enterprises partake in tax avoidance, the corporation adheres to Indonesian tax legislation to circumvent legal complications and preserve its reputation. This indicates that enterprises with foreign ownership must exercise caution to avoid risking their relationships with the government and the community (Marfiana & Andriyanto, 2021).

On the other hand, good corporate governance, characterized by openness, effective supervision, and accountability, functions as a strategy to mitigate the propensity for tax avoidance. Numerous studies suggest that firms exhibiting strong governance are more

likely to fulfill their tax responsibilities and demonstrate social responsibility (Tania, 2020). Corporate governance denotes the framework of regulations, procedures, and practices employed to administer and supervise a corporation. An effective and transparent governance framework can diminish the motivation for aggressive tax avoidance, as stakeholders—including the board of commissioners, management, and shareholders—are more inclined to adhere to current regulations and prioritize compliance over immediate benefits derived from tax avoidance. Therefore, the quality of corporate governance can play a moderating role in the relationship between family ownership structure and foreign ownership on tax avoidance. This also represents the novelty of this research, which is expected to contribute to studies related to tax avoidance.

This study highlights the occurrence of disproportionate tax objectives and outcomes from 2018 to 2022, when a greater number failed to achieve the targets. Moreover, prior studies regarding the impact of ownership structure on tax avoidance did not consider corporate governance as a moderating factor. This study examines the moderating influence that corporate governance has on the relationship between ownership structure and tax avoidance. This research was conducted on manufacturing sector companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange from 2018 to 2022, considering that this sector is the company sector with the highest capitalization, so there is the possibility of tax avoidance practices occurring. This issue will result in discrepancies between the proposed research and prior studies regarding population, sample, and research timeline. By considering the existing research factors, the research questions of this study are (1) What is the influence of family ownership and foreign ownership on tax avoidance? (2) What is the moderating role of Good Corporate Governance in predicting tax avoidance.

Literature Review

Agency theory

Agency Theory is a framework used in numerous prior research about tax avoidance. Jensen and Meckling explain that agency relationships arise when one or more individuals delegate tasks to another individual, granting them the authority to make decisions. Under these conditions, it is impossible to guarantee that the agent will act in the best interests of the principal (Tania, 2020). This condition can lead to an agency problem, causing the principal and agent to have different goals. The agent no longer works in accordance with the interests of the principal. Agency problems are divided into two types: type-one agency problem and type-two agency problem. Type-one agency problems occur when conflicts arise between owners outside the company and managers who run the company. Type one agency problems generally occur in companies with a dispersed ownership structure. Whereas the type two agency problem occurs when there is a conflict of interest between the majority shareholders and the minority shareholders (Marfiana & Andriyanto, 2021).

The conflict frequently arises from different incentives between the two parties. Shareholders aim to enhance the company's worth and adhere to legal requirements, including tax duties, whereas management could be motivated to make self-serving decisions, such as aggressive tax avoidance, potentially boosting the company's short-

term profits (Prismanitra & Sukirman, 2021). The agency problem is exacerbated in family and foreign ownership systems, as proprietors have increased control over decision-making and management. Family proprietors frequently maintain direct oversight of the enterprise and prioritize the long-term viability of both the company and the family's wealth. Conversely, firms having foreign ownership may be more predisposed to pursue tax reductions via international tax strategies or transfer pricing, thereby exacerbating agency conflicts between managers and shareholders (principals).

Compliance theory

Compliance theory elucidates a scenario wherein an individual adheres to an instruction. Taxpayer compliance refers to the efforts of taxpayers to comprehend and meet their obligations in accordance with established guidelines and relevant laws and regulations. Taxpayer compliance and compliance theory are intimately interconnected, as taxpayer compliance delineates the conditions under which taxpayers can meet their obligations and assert their right to pay taxes. Conversely, compliance theory elucidates the conditions under which an individual adheres to rules or laws. Additional ideas concerning taxpayer compliance encompass social learning, prospect theory, and attribution theory (Marfiana & Andriyanto, 2021). According to Minister of Finance Regulation No. 192/PMK.03/2007 regarding Taxpayers with specific criteria for the preliminary reimbursement of tax overpayment, Compliant Taxpayers are those who meet the following conditions:

- a. Timely submission of the notice letter.
- b. Accurately compute and remit taxes punctually.
- c. There are no tax arrears for any tax categories, save for those for which the taxpayer has obtained authorization to defer or reschedule payments.
- d. Financial statements audited by a public accountant or government financial oversight agency with an unqualified opinion for three successive years.
- e. I have not been convicted of any criminal offense related to taxation by a court ruling with permanent legal effect in the past five years.

Compliance theory focuses on how companies adhere to applicable regulations, including tax regulations, by considering internal and external factors that influence corporate behavior. In the context of corporate governance, this theory posits that companies with good governance are more likely to comply with tax regulations due to oversight mechanisms that reduce the chances of engaging in aggressive tax avoidance. Good corporate governance can serve as a mechanism that moderates the relationship between family ownership structure, foreign ownership, and tax avoidance.

Legitimacy theory

Another fundamental principle of the research is legitimacy theory, which posits that a firm would conduct its commercial activities in alignment with prevailing norms and regulations to attain community legitimacy. The legitimacy theory states that companies strive to obtain legitimacy from society and other stakeholders by adhering to existing social standards and regulations. In the realm of taxation, this legitimacy signifies that corporations are obligated to remit taxes in accordance with the relevant legislation and refrain from employing aggressive tax avoidance strategies. Tax avoidance, while legally acceptable in certain instances, may harm a company's reputation if viewed as an effort to shirk societal responsibilities (Marfiana & Andriyanto, 2021).

Legitimacy theory examines how companies try to acquire and sustain social legitimacy by conforming to established social norms and regulations, particularly in taxes. In this context, companies try to cultivate a positive image among the public, regulators, and other stakeholders by complying with relevant legislation and eschewing actions that could tarnish their reputation, such as tax avoidance (Prismanitra & Sukirman, 2021). In this context, effective corporate governance is crucial in mitigating tax avoidance by ensuring that enterprises adhere to legal requirements and acquire the requisite legitimacy for sustainable operations.

Previous Research Results

Numerous studies on this subject have been undertaken by prior academics, like Nurjanah & Aligarh (2021) shows that family ownership has a positive effect on tax avoidance. Meanwhile, Panjaitan et al. (2021) found that family ownership has a negative effect on tax avoidance. The other results as expressed by Tarmizi et al. (2023) did not find any influence of family ownership on tax avoidance. The difference in the findings of this study urges additional inquiry into the impact of family ownership on tax avoidance when assessed under the current situation.

The study by Suranta et al. (2020) showed that the structure of foreign ownership has a positive effect on tax avoidance, where the greater the structure of foreign ownership, the higher the company to avoid tax, while the investigations by Tanujaya et al. (2021) yielded contrasting findings, suggesting that foreign ownership does not significantly impact tax avoidance. The gap in the findings of this study necessitates additional inquiry into the impact of family ownership on tax avoidance when analyzed under present circumstances.

The study by Marfiana & Andriyanto (2021), referenced in this research, indicates that family, foreign, and government ownership positively influences tax avoidance. Nevertheless, multiple large shareholders (MLS) effectively diminish their association with tax avoidance. This presents an opportunity for researchers to utilize corporate governance as a moderating variable.

Framework and Hypothesis

Framework of Thought

Using corporate governance as a moderating variable, researchers have proposed various options, including the influence of family and foreign ownership structures on tax avoidance. The aim of this research is to ascertain the impact of ownership structure, namely family or foreign ownership, on tax avoidance. This study seeks to examine the moderating effect of corporate governance on the connection between these factors.

Figure 1. Framework of Thought

Hypothesis Development

Family Ownership on Tax Avoidance

Marfiana & Andriyanto (2021) identify two categories of agency problems: type one arises from conflicts of interest between external owners and the company's managers, while type two emerges from conflicts between majority and minority shareholders. Family-owned companies are anticipated to reduce agency concerns, as a shared objective between the principal and the agent facilitates easier management oversight. Family-operated enterprise In addition to ownership, the family also serves as controllers of the company, creating chances for tax avoidance tactics. Tax avoidance is significantly positively impacted by family ownership.

H1: Family ownership positively impacts the tax avoidance.

Foreign Ownership on Tax Avoidance

Foreign investors anticipate achieving superior returns on their capital investments in a company. The agency theory elucidates that the employment contract connection comprises shareholders (principal) as the grantor of authority and management (agent) as the recipient

of authority (Ramdhania et al., 2020). The agency dilemma stems from the divergent aims of management and shareholders, as the growing prevalence of foreign ownership in a corporation may impact decision-making to favor the interests of foreign shareholders. The elevated degree of foreign ownership exacerbates the occurrence of tax avoidance practices.

H₂: Foreign ownership positively impacts the tax avoidance.

Moderating Variable of Corporate Governance with the Impact of Family Ownership on Tax Avoidance

Family enterprises frequently prioritize long-term sustainability and company reputation, particularly since the owning family serves as principal stakeholders in operations and decision-making. They are more inclined to preserve their social legitimacy by ensuring the company complies with tax legislation to mitigate reputational concerns that could impact the company's long-term viability (Sujendra et al., 2019). Nevertheless, family-owned enterprises with inadequate governance may resort to tax evasion for personal benefit; so, effective corporate governance is essential to prioritize tax compliance over just short-term profits.

H₃: The association between family ownership and tax avoidance is moderated by corporate governance.

Moderating Variable of Corporate Governance with the Impact of Foreign Ownership on Tax Avoidance

Companies with foreign ownership typically prioritize tax optimization and exploit disparities in tax rates among nations through strategies such as transfer pricing or profit shifting to jurisdictions with lower tax rates. Tax evasion may jeopardize the company's legitimacy among local stakeholders, particularly if such practices are perceived as harmful to the host country (Sujendra et al., 2019). Consequently, effective corporate governance may uphold the company's legitimacy by ensuring that tax avoidance is conducted in a manner that does not compromise the company's reputation or deteriorate its ties with the government and society.

H₄: The association between foreign ownership and tax avoidance is moderated by corporate governance.

Methodology

Research type and approach

This study gathers secondary data from the annual reports of all manufacturing companies on the Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX) spanning a five-year period from 2018 to 2022, employing quantitative research technique and approach. The choice of research subjects concerning corporations listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange is attributed to the prevalence of the tax avoidance phenomenon in Indonesia. This tax avoiding strategy could compromise the Indonesian government's ability to secure funding for national development. This warrants investigation due to the multitude of tax avoidance strategies employed by corporations. While these practices may not contravene

legislation, tax avoidance can nonetheless adversely affect the government and impede the nation's progress.

The involvement of internal parties within a firm is equally significant in the tax avoidance committed by corporate entities. The composition of share ownership within a corporation can impact managers' decisions to partake in tax avoidance activities. The execution of governance inside a corporation can influence tax avoidance behaviors; effective governance reduces the probability of such acts, and conversely, ineffective governance increases it.

Operational Variables

The operational variables of the research model are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Variable Definitions and Operations

Variables	Definition	Indicator
Tax Avoidance (Y)	This tax avoidance is a legal strategy employed by the firm to minimize its tax liability by exploiting legislative gaps (Ouyang et al., 2020)	Proxied by Cash ETR, where the cash effective tax rate is calculated based on the amount of tax cash paid by the company in the current year, the smaller the CETR value, the greater the company's tax avoidance, and conversely, the larger the CETR value, the smaller the company's tax avoidance. The value of CETR ranges from more than 0 to less than 1. This measurement is used to describe the tax avoidance activities of companies; Cash ETR can reflect the actual rate applicable to the company's income based on the amount of tax that has been paid. The higher the CETR percentage, approaching the corporate income tax rate of 25%, indicates that the level of tax avoidance by the company is lower. Conversely, the lower the CETR percentage, the higher the level of tax avoidance by the company. (Ibrahim et al., 2021)
Family Ownership (X1)	This family ownership refers to a company where the shareholding exceeds ten percent and the management of the company involves family relationships. (Marfiana & Andriyanto, 2021)	Percentage of family-owned shares to total issued shares. (Al Amosh & Khatib, 2022)

Variables	Definition	Indicator
Foreign Ownership (X2)	Foreign ownership is a number of shares or capital sourced from foreign countries, where foreign individuals or legal entities in Indonesia have part or all of their capital from foreign parties. (Marfiana & Andriyanto, 2021)	The percentage of the shares owned by foreigners to the total number of issued shares. (Al Amosh & Khatib, 2022)
Corporate Governance (Z)	Corporate Governance is the structure implemented in a company to achieve the company's objectives. (Marfiana & Andriyanto, 2021)	Corporate Governance is measured with 15 indicator items from the Indonesia Corporate Governance Index (ICGI). Consists of (1) Code of ethics, (2) Anti-corruption, (3) Insider trading, (4) Largest shareholder, (5) Free float (Public share ownership), (6) Employees share ownerships, (7) CSR, (8) Whistleblowing, (9) Sanctions, (10) Big4 auditors, (11) Disclosure of the ultimate beneficiary shareholders, (12) Independent director, (13) Independent commissioner, (14) Size of the board of director, (15) Size of the board of commissioner. One point is given for each fulfilled indicator. The total points earned will be divided by the total number of indicators, which is 15 indicators. (Tanjung, 2020)

Population and Sample

The population used in this study consists of all manufacturing companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX) from 2018 to 2022, totalling 161 companies. The sampling technique used in this study is purposive sampling, which involves the specific selection of samples based on certain criteria. Sample selection is carried out based on considerations and meets the following criteria:

Table 3. Research Sample

No.	Criteria	Total
1	Manufacturing Companies Listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange Until 2022	161
2	Manufacturing companies that did not publish consecutive financial and annual reports during 2018-2022	(32)
3	Manufacturing companies that experienced losses during 2018-2022	(52)
4	Companies without family ownership during 2018-2022	(25)
5	Total research sample	52
5	Total observational data 52 companies x 5 years	260

The final sample for this research comprises 52 companies over a 5-year period, yielding a total of 260 observational data points. Data sources were obtained through the company's website as well as the Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX) website, which is www.idx.co.id.

Data Analysis Technique

Statistical test using panel data estimation method. The regression model can be formulated in the following equation:

$$\text{Model 1: } Y = \alpha + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \varepsilon$$

$$\text{Model 2: } Y = \alpha + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 Z + \varepsilon$$

Using panel data, we generate different intercept and slope coefficients for each object and time period. There are several methods that can be used to estimate the panel data regression model, namely the approach Common Effects, Fixed Effects, and Random Effects. Tests will be carried out using the eViews software. To choose the best model, it can be done with three tests, namely chow test, Hausman test, and Lagrange Multiplier test.

Moderated regression analysis (MRA) is an interaction test analysis used to obtain an overview of the impact of exports, imports, and economic growth on exchange rates, as well as to determine whether moderating variables can influence the relationship between dependent and independent variables. The advantage of this test is that it provides results for the moderation variable, indicating whether it strengthens or weakens the influence of the dependent variable on the independent variable. The MRA equation model can be expressed as follows:

$$\text{Model 3: } Y = \alpha + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 Z + \beta_4 X_1 * Z + \beta_5 X_2 * Z + \varepsilon$$

Results and discussion

Descriptive Statistics

The Table 4 represents the descriptive statistics for all variables. The study reveals that companies with family ownership have a higher average value of 70.39%, compared to the chemical sub-sector company's 99.49%. This indicates that family ownership tends to minimize agency problems, as the owner and management are the same party. Foreign ownership is also higher, with a higher average value of 48.77% in cosmetics and household goods companies and a higher maximum value of 98.99% in precious metals and similar sub-sector companies. This indicates that companies with high foreign share ownership tend to increase tax avoidance behavior.

Table 4. Descriptive statistics of the study

No	Description	Family Ownership	Foreign Ownership	Tax Avoidance	Governance
1	Mean	0,703902	0,487707	0,253385	0,824615
2	Median	0,748331	0,412311	0,240000	0,870000
3	Maximum	0,994987	0,989949	0,970000	0,930000
4	Minimum	0,223607	0,223607	0,010000	0,530000
5	Std. Dev.	0,217618	0,247902	0,120245	0,090461
6	<i>Observation</i>	260	260	260	260

The study also measures tax avoidance using the cash effective tax rate (CETR), with an average value of 25.33% and a maximum value of 97% less than 100%. The lower the CETR value, the lower the tax avoidance actions. The Indonesian Corporate Governance Index (ICGI) shows an average governance value of 82.46%, with a maximum value of 93%. This indicates that companies with high governance tend to implement exemplary international practices, despite not yet being required in the Financial Services Authority Regulation (POJK) Number 21 / POJK.04 / 2015.

Best Model Selection

This study uses model selection analysis to examine panel data regression for data description. The subsequent outcomes of the model selection analysis test are presented.

This study uses the fixed effect model for its investigation of model selection. The subsequent phase involves the conventional assumption test of the data. The classical assumption test evaluates the quality of the data obtained by the researcher to determine its suitability for use as a reference in the study.

Table 5. Best Model Selection Test

No.	Description	Test	Hypothesis	Probability	Selected Model
1	Model 1	Chow	H ₀ : CEM	0,0022	Fixed Effects Model (FEM)
			H _a : FEM		
		Hausman	H ₀ : REM	0,0141	
			H _a : FEM		
		Lagrange Multiplier	H ₀ : CEM	0,0203	
			H _a : REM		
2	Model 2	Chow	H ₀ : CEM	0,0030	Fixed Effects Model (FEM)
			H _a : FEM		
		Hausman	H ₀ : REM	0,0401	
			H _a : FEM		
		Lagrange Multiplier	H ₀ : CEM	0,0245	
			H _a : REM		
3	Model 3	Chow	H ₀ : CEM	0,0026	Fixed Effects Model (FEM)
			H _a : FEM		
		Hausman	H ₀ : REM	0,0500	
			H _a : FEM		
		Lagrange Multiplier	H ₀ : CEM	0,0228	
			H _a : REM		

Hypothesis Test

The analysis results for family ownership, foreign ownership, corporate governance, and tax avoidance are presented in table 6.

Based on table 6, it is known that in model 1 equation, the probability value is 0.5290, which is higher than the significance level ($0.5290 > 0.05$). Similarly, in model equation 2, the probability value is 0.5811, which is higher than the significance level ($0.5811 > 0.05$). It is concluded that the family ownership variable does not have a positive and significant effect on the tax avoidance. Therefore, the first hypothesis (H1) is rejected.

Based on the test results in Table 6, the probability value of model equation 1 is 0.0050, which is less than the 10% significance level ($0.0050 < 0.10$). Meanwhile, in equation 2, the probability value is 0.0051, which is smaller than the significance level ($0.0059 < 0.10$). It is concluded that the foreign ownership variable has a positive and significant effect on tax avoidance. Therefore, the second hypothesis (H2) is accepted.

The results of the governance test as a moderating variable between family ownership and tax avoidance in model equation 3 obtained a probability value of 0.2670, which is higher than the significance level ($0.2670 > 0.05$). It can be concluded that corporate governance does not moderate the relationship between family ownership and tax avoidance. Therefore, the third hypothesis (H3) is rejected.

The governance test results, serving as a moderating variable between foreign ownership and tax avoidance in model equation 3, yielded a probability value of 0.5791, exceeding the significance level ($0.5791 > 0.05$). It can be concluded that corporate governance does not influence the relationship between foreign ownership and tax avoidance. Therefore, the fourth hypothesis (H4) is rejected.

Table 6. Analysis Result of Family Ownership, Foreign Ownership, Corporate Governance, and Tax Avoidance

Variable	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Moderation	Result
C	2,9485	2,542357	0,3095		
	(0,0036)	(0,0117)	(0,7572)		
X1	-0,6306	-0,5527	0,9672		
	(0,5290)	(0,5811)	(0,3346)		
X2	2,8357	2,8298	1,9552		
	(0,0050)	(0,0051)	(0,0519)		
Z		-1,2475	0,3840		
		(0,2136)	(0,7013)		
Z on Y		-3,9762	0,3840		
		(0,0165)	(0,7013)		
X1*Z			-1,1129	Not Sig.	Predictor Moderator
			(0,2670)		
X2*Z			-0,5556	Not Sig.	Homologizer Moderator
			(0,5791)		
R-squared	0,312300	0,317482	0,32184		
Adjusted R-squared	0,135367	0,137696	0,134761		
F-statistic	1,765079	1,765892	1,720344		
Prob (Statistic)	0,002673	0,002526	0,003463		

Family Ownership and Tax Avoidance

The findings indicate that family ownership has a negative and insignificant impact, suggesting that enterprises with a family ownership structure are inclined to reduce tax avoidance methods. These findings align with compliance theory, which posits that taxpayers conform to a well-defined standard or legislation produced and disseminated by the pertinent authority or institution within its domain. Family-owned enterprises exhibit a greater propensity to remit elevated taxes instead of incurring penalties and risking reputational harm from tax avoidance, which could result in audits by tax authorities (Marfiana & Andriyanto, 2021). This finding is corroborated by research indicating that family ownership adversely affects tax avoidance, as evidenced by studies conducted by Panjaitan et al. (2021) and Tarmizi et al. (2023). Nonetheless, the findings of this study contradict the research undertaken by Nurjanah & Aligarh (2021), which indicate that family ownership positively influences tax avoidance.

Foreign Ownership and Tax Avoidance

The findings indicate that foreign ownership positively and significantly influences enterprises, which are inclined to adopt tax avoidance strategies to maximize revenues. Through these tax avoidance strategies, enterprises with foreign ownership will yield substantial returns relative to their incurred expenses. These findings align with studies indicating that foreign ownership positively influences tax avoidance (Suranta et al., 2020; Marfiana & Andriyanto, 2021). Nonetheless, the findings from the studies by Tanujaya et al. (2021) indicate that foreign ownership does not influence tax avoidance.

The Role of Corporate Governance

The hypothesis test results indicate that governance exerts a negative and insignificant effect on the relationship between family ownership and tax avoidance, with governance in this study categorized as a predictor-type moderating variable. This suggests that the moderating variable can be recognized when the first coefficient is significant but the second coefficient lacks statistical significance, indicating that governance, in this equation, functions as a predictor variable inside the established model. The establishment of governance policies within a corporation might mitigate tax evasion activities. This study indicates that, irrespective of the degree of family ownership in a firm, it can mitigate tax evasion activities undertaken by the company. Nevertheless, the enforcement of governance does not diminish the tax evasion activities conducted by the corporation.

This suggests that a family ownership structure in a firm tends to prioritize the preservation of the company's reputation over engaging in tax evasion practices that could jeopardize its long-term sustainability. The absence of family ownership structures' influence on tax evasion within the company indicates that management's governance strategies are ineffective in mitigating tax evasion activities.

Additional findings indicate that company governance weakens and does not significantly mitigate the impact of foreign ownership on tax avoidance. This study clarified that, irrespective of the degree of foreign ownership in a company, it cannot mitigate the tax avoidance activities conducted by the company. Nonetheless, the establishment of governance might mitigate the tax avoidance activities conducted by the organization.

This suggests that the current foreign ownership structure within a corporation generally promotes sound governance; nonetheless, it is inevitable that foreign-owned companies also want to maximize earnings to minimize tax liabilities. To align with the interests of foreign-owned enterprises, they will minimize expenses through tax avoidance strategies. In contrast to family ownership, which emphasizes the company's reputation and long-term sustainability. Tanujaya et al. (2021) asserts that firms with foreign ownership structures choose tax avoidance chances over preserving their company brand. Consequently, while the foreign ownership structure affects tax avoidance activities, the enforcement of governance standards by management can mitigate such acts within those organizations.

Conclusion

Based on empirical data, the results of the analysis and discussion of the problem formulation using panel data analysis, it can be concluded that family ownership has a negative effect on tax avoidance, as it tends to maintain a company's reputation by complying with regulations. Conversely, foreign ownership has a positive effect, as companies with foreign ownership focus on gaining profits and reducing costs, including tax avoidance. Governance cannot moderate the effect of family ownership on tax avoidance, but good governance can weaken it. Transparency in a company can balance information ownership and interests, reducing agency problems like tax avoidance. Overall, the study suggests that both family and foreign ownership structures have different effects on tax avoidance.

The study highlights the significance of a corporation fulfilling its tax obligations to ensure long-term viability. Mitigating tax avoidance risk is essential for investment security. The board of commissioners is essential in directing management and enforcing effective governance in accordance with regulations. The results highlight the necessity for investors examine financial statements and annual reports, as smaller tax payments increase the likelihood of tax avoidance.

The findings of this research are anticipated to provide input and assessment information for the government concerning corporations or taxpayers, which will influence the state's revenue derived from tax payments. The findings of this research are anticipated to serve as a foundation for governmental deliberation to elucidate and effectively tackle the enforcement of regulations pertaining to Tax Avoidance, as outlined in Article 18 of Law Number 36 of 2008, which amends Law Number 7 of 1983 concerning Income Tax. This regulation pertains to the Specific Anti-Avoidance Rule and was last amended by Law Number 7 of 2021 regarding the Harmonization of Tax Regulations (Income Tax Law), which empowers the government to negotiate agreements with other nations to avert double taxation and tax avoidance, thereby enhancing transparency and minimizing corporate tax avoidance or evasion activities.

Recommendations

This research is inevitably constrained by several issues that may be resolved through future research; the suggestions made in this research may help in future research. Suggestions for this research are:

1. Further inquiry is advised to do research not only in the manufacturing sector, but it is anticipated that the study sample would encompass organizations in both the financial and non-financial sectors.
2. Further study is advised to incorporate control variables, facilitating a comparison of findings across studies employing control variables and those that do not. To observe the amount of the control variable's influence on the research outcomes.

References

- Al Amosh, H., & Khatib, S. F. (2022). Ownership structure and environmental, social and governance performance disclosure: The moderating role of board independence. *Journal of Business and Socio-Economic Development*, 2(1), 49–66. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JBSED-07-2021-0094>
- Chakroun, S., & Ben Amar, A. (2024). The IFRS adoption, corporate tax avoidance and the moderating effect of family ownership. *International Journal of Law and Management*, 66(4), 347–367. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJLMA-06-2023-0135>
- Chalevas, C. G., Doukakis, L. C., Karampinis, N. I., & Pavlopoulou, O. C. (2024). The impact of family ownership on tax avoidance: International evidence. *International Review of Financial Analysis*, 94, Article 103317. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.irfa.2024.103317>
- Hasan, I., Kim, I., Teng, H., & Wu, Q. (2022). The effect of foreign institutional ownership on corporate tax avoidance: International evidence. *Journal of International Accounting, Auditing and Taxation*, 46, Article 100440. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.intaccaudtax.2021.100440>
- Ibrahim, R., Sutrisno, T., & Rusydi, M. K. (2021). The influence factors of tax avoidance in Indonesia. *International Journal of Research in Business and Social Science*, 10(5), 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.20525/ijrbs.v10i5.1295>
- Koay, G. Y., & Sapiei, N. S. (2024). The role of corporate governance on corporate tax avoidance: A developing country perspective. *Journal of Accounting in Emerging Economies*, 14(5), 957–977. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JAEE-01-2023-0022>
- Kovermann, J., & Wendt, M. (2019). Tax avoidance in family firms: Evidence from large private firms. *Journal of Contemporary Accounting & Economics*, 15(2), 145–157. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcae.2019.04.003>
- Krisyadi, R., & Anita, A. (2022). Pengaruh pengungkapan tanggung jawab sosial perusahaan, kepemilikan keluarga, dan tata kelola perusahaan terhadap penghindaran pajak [The influence of corporate social responsibility disclosure, family ownership, and corporate governance on tax avoidance]. *Owner*, 6(1), 416–425. <https://doi.org/10.33395/owner.v6i1.599>
- Marfiana, A., & Andriyanto, T. (2021). Pengaruh struktur kepemilikan perusahaan terhadap tax avoidance di Indonesia dengan corporate governance sebagai variabel moderasi [The influence of company ownership structure on tax avoidance in Indonesia with corporate governance as a moderating variable]. *Jurnal Pajak dan Keuangan Negara*, 3(1), 178–196. <https://doi.org/10.31092/jpkn.v3i1.1226>
- Nurdiansyah, R. (2023). Factors causing tax avoidance practices in multinational companies: Evidence from Indonesia. *International Journal of Research in*

Business and Social Science, 12(3), 391–398.
<https://doi.org/10.20525/ijrbs.v12i3.2565>

- Nurjanah, S., & Aligarh, F. (2021). Family ownership, independent commissioners, audit quality, and tax avoidance in Indonesia. *JIFA (Journal of Islamic Finance and Accounting)*, 4(2), 82–93. <https://doi.org/10.22515/jifa.v4i2.4378>
- Ouyang, C., Xiong, J., & Huang, K. (2020). Do multiple large shareholders affect tax avoidance? Evidence from China. *International Review of Economics & Finance*, 67, 207–224. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iref.2019.12.009>
- Panjaitan, A., Maksum, A., & Abubakar, E. (2021). The influence of corporate social responsibility, corporate characteristic, family ownership, profitability and corporate governance on tax avoidance. *Jurnal Mantik*, 4(4), 2331–2335. <https://doi.org/10.35335/mantik.vol4.2021.1141.pp2331-2335>
- Prismanitra, K., & Sukirman, S. (2021). The determinants of tax avoidance with good corporate governance as a moderating variable. *Accounting Analysis Journal*, 10(2), 101–107. <https://doi.org/10.15294/aaaj.v10i2.47342>
- Ramdhania, D. L., Yulia, E., & Leon, F. M. (2020). Pengaruh gender diversity dewan direksi dan CEO terhadap nilai perusahaan sektor properti, real estate dan pembangunan di Indonesia [The influence of board and CEO gender diversity on firm value in the property, real estate, and construction sector in Indonesia]. *Jurnal Wacana Ekonomi*, 19(2), 82–94. <https://doi.org/10.52434/jwe.v19i2.891>
- Sastrodiharjo, I., & Mukti, A. H. (2024). Exploring the intricacies of tax planning: A novel insight from the Indonesian context. *Cogent Business & Management*, 11(1), Article 2348709. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311975.2024.2348709>
- Shin, H. (2020). Avoiding inheritance taxes in family firms. *Financial Management*, 49(4), 1051–1082. <https://doi.org/10.1111/fima.12308>
- Sujendra, I. M., Made, N., Ratnadi, D., Mediatrix, M., Sari, R., & Rasmini, N. K. (2019). The effect of corporate social responsibility disclosure, family ownership, and good corporate governance on tax avoidance. *Research Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 10(22), 88–95. <https://doi.org/10.7176/RJFA>
- Suranta, E., Midiastuty, P., & Hasibuan, H. R. (2020). The effect of foreign ownership and foreign board commissioners on tax avoidance. *Journal of Economics, Business, and Accountancy Ventura*, 22(3), 309–318. <https://doi.org/10.14414/jebav.v22i3.2143>
- Tania, F. F. (2020). The effect of corporate governance on tax avoidance: Evidence from Indonesia. *Management & Economics Research Journal*, 2(4), 66–85. <https://doi.org/10.48100/merj.v2i4.126>

- Tanjung, M. (2020). A cross-firm analysis of corporate governance compliance and performance in Indonesia. *Managerial Auditing Journal*, 35(5), 621–643.
<https://doi.org/10.1108/MAJ-06-2019-2328>
- Tanujaya, K., Ratna, D., & Suhardjo, I. (2021). Pengaruh struktur kepemilikan, karakteristik dewan, dan kesulitan finansial terhadap penghindaran pajak [The influence of ownership structure, board characteristics, and financial distress on tax avoidance]. *Global Financial Accounting Journal*, 5(2), 171–185.
<https://doi.org/10.37253/gfa.v5i2.6094>
- Tarmizi, A., Perkasa, D. H., Meliantari, D., & Wahdiawati, S. A. (2023). The effect of institutional ownership, family ownership, and thin capitalization on tax avoidance. *KnE Social Sciences*, 8(12), 1–10.
<https://doi.org/10.18502/kss.v8i12.13645>

<p>COPYRIGHTS</p> <p>©2025 The Author(s). This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY 4.0), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, as long as the original authors and source are cited. No permission is required from the authors or the publishers.</p>	
<p>HOW TO CITE THIS ARTICLE</p> <p>Agusti, A. Isma, Handajani, L. and Ardan Putraa, I. Nyoman Nugraha (2025). Interaction of Governance in the Influence of Ownership Structure on Tax Avoidance. <i>International Journal of Management, Accounting and Economics</i>, 12(5), 761-779.</p> <p>DOI: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15635326</p> <p>URL: https://www.ijmae.com/article_220923.html</p>	